

MEASURES TO BE IMPLEMENTED ON THE PROTECTION OF LABOR AND THE SAFE CONDUCT OF RESCUE WORKS

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Safety rules are an integral part of all types of rescue operations, and compliance with them not only ensures our health, but also improves the efficiency of rescue operations. For this purpose, the newly appointed rescuers in the field are trained in safety rules and compliance with them from the initial training stage. These rules, in turn, are divided into several types (electrical, fire safety, at work, in rescue operations, etc.), and each of them, in turn, is of special importance, and all together serve to ensure the safety of our activities.

When training rescuers according to safety rules, first of all, it is necessary to fully comply with the entry instructions, to ensure that they can fulfill the requirements of the instructions without words and mistakes. Because it is this instruction that serves as a "bridge" for other types of safety rules that a rescuer will encounter during his work. A lifeguard who successfully passes this stage is more likely to learn and fully comply with the safety rules that will be followed in the future. Otherwise, the rescuer may have the idea that certain rules must be followed, and others can be ignored. This can lead to the occurrence of various unpleasant events in the future.

It is difficult to imagine our rescue work without various special equipment. A large part of the safety regulations requires mastering the procedure of working with them and increasing the skill of being able to use them correctly. In addition, it should not be forgotten that we also use mountain rescue equipment when it is necessary to carry out radiation, chemical, biological (bacteriological) rescue and other operations. This requires additional knowledge and skills (ability to use mountain rescue equipment) from team rescuers. In addition to ensuring our safety, the correct use of special equipment and other technical means in rescue operations, in compliance with the established rules, also ensures that these equipment will serve us for a long time.

Radiation, chemical, biological (bacteriological) protection work has a number of specific aspects of safety rules, which require us to take measures that are not necessary for us in other types of rescue work. In addition, it should be noted that most of the general safety rules are related to the implementation of a number of rescue operations (with the exception of diving operations).

It is necessary to combine the training of safety regulations with the rescuers in the field with various special tactical training exercises. In the tests of professional training, special attention should be paid to this area, and the lifeguard with a low score should be dealt with individually. Because regularly improving the knowledge of rescuers on safety rules, focusing special attention on real situations that may occur during rescue operations, is one of the urgent tasks of today.

We cannot say that the topics discussed in this methodological guide fully cover safety rules in radiation, chemical, biological (bacteriological) protection work. This is due to various factors, i.e. the increase in the type and method of our rescue operations, the acquisition of new modern equipment and techniques, etc. as it continues, the safety regulations will increase accordingly.

In the system of the Ministry of Emergencies, a number of regulatory and legal documents have been adopted in order to protect labor, prevent various disappointments that may occur, and organize safe rescue operations.

Timely implementation of appropriate measures to ensure safe conduct of labor protection and rescue operations at the sites serves to prevent various disappointments that may occur. The events to be organized in this regard should be in accordance with the requirements. Of course, in the organization of work in this regard, it is necessary to consistently approach the goals and tasks and basic principles set by the ministry in this regard. The policy of the Ministry in the field of labor protection is based on the following principles:

- stability of the employee's life and health in relation to the results of service in the ministerial system;
- to establish a single procedure and rules in the field of labor protection in enterprises and organizations of the ministerial system, regardless of the organizational-legal and ownership form and departmental subordination;
- control the fulfillment of labor protection requirements in all enterprises and organizations of the ministry system;
- extensive use of scientific and technical achievements and advanced local and foreign experiences in labor protection;
- free provision of rescuers with special clothing, personal protection and treatment-prophylactic means;
- every accident in the service, examination and recording of occupational diseases, giving information about the level of injuries and occupational diseases, etc.

It is appropriate to plan all measures related to labor protection in regional departments and constituent structures based on the above principles.

For this, first of all, it is necessary to appoint qualified employees with many years of experience to be in charge of conducting these events on a regular basis. This employee coordinates the work in this regard, develops the necessary service

documents, conducts "Introduction" instructions with all employees, monitors their compliance with these rules, and reports to the manager on the completed work.

According to the relevant order of the Minister of Emergency Situations, labor protection guidelines are divided into the following types:

- entry (at the time of recruitment) - according to the requirements of general safety (fire safety, use of electrical equipment, etc.) with newly recruited rescuers to the regional administration and structural structures;
- carried out at the workplace - rescue team, which in turn is divided into three:
 - initial guidance at the workplace - taking into account the special features of the position and the type of work, on the security requirements of the period when the duties of the position are being transferred;
 - periodical guidance at the workplace - for a specified period of time by the heads of the regional administration and structural structure;
 - extraordinary instruction - is given when an injury or accident occurs during the service, when you are transferred from one position to another position, when you receive new special equipment or when safety rules are violated.

As mentioned above, the entry instruction is conducted by the designated responsible officer, while the instructions at the workplace should be conducted directly by the squad commander and group commander (commander). For this, it is necessary to develop safety rules for rescuers, which include the specific characteristics of their duties and the aspects of danger.

After all the necessary documents and various guidelines have been developed, one of the main activities is to increase the knowledge and practical skills of lifeguards, that is, to prepare them for safe work. This is a rather complex process, which includes several activities, and in its implementation, not only the responsible personnel, but also the rescuers themselves are required to be equally active.

We would not be wrong if we say that the work of ensuring labor safety of rescuers begins with the determination of their worthiness for the positions they occupy. When choosing rescuers, work in this regard should be done more carefully. For this:

- psychological and physical examination of new recruits and assessment of professional aptitude;
- learning experience, industry knowledge, qualifications and skills;
- it is necessary to control the process of getting used to the profession of lifeguards who have passed the tests and are appointed to the position.
- Training of rescuers in labor protection, continuous improvement of their knowledge in this regard includes the following processes:

- practice at the workplace - in the period before rescuers are put on duty (preliminary training on the premises);
- pairing a new employee with an experienced, qualified specialist (the mentor-apprenticeship tradition);
- vocational training.

A rescuer who has been assigned to a position and successfully passed the initial training and familiarization process can be transferred to the next stage of training. At this stage, rescuers are trained in various educational institutions:

- initial training - conducted at the Institute of Civil Protection on the basis of a specially defined Program, with special attention paid to safety rules and their specific aspects in rescue operations;
- training - conducted at the Institute of Civil Protection on the basis of a specially defined Program, during the training course, safety rules for working with newly acquired special equipment are conveyed to rescuers, and knowledge of safety rules of rescuers is tested;
- in the educational institutions of various ministries and departments - lifeguards are carried out on the basis of special instructions in the field of rescuers, and attention is paid to exactly one direction. For example: in the Republic of Shoshilinch Medical Aid Training Center, rescuers are systematically trained to teach first aid to people injured in accidents, etc.

Apart from these, participation in various Command and Special-Tactical training exercises held in the field is of great importance in improving the knowledge of rescuers in this regard.

Part of the activities to ensure the safety of rescuers should be aimed at ensuring the suitability of special equipment and personal protective equipment. For this purpose, the suitability and completeness of special equipment and personal protective equipment should be checked regularly (at the time of acceptance of each duty shift). In this process, it is necessary not to rush, to carefully conduct the inspection and to make sure that all the parts and details in the set of equipment are available, their serviceability and free from various mechanical damages. It is necessary to determine the amount of reserves of air balloons, the fullness of batteries of observation devices and the serviceability of electric batteries, and to provide them with technical and other various services on the appointed day of every month.

It should be remembered that we cannot guarantee that a rescuer who has acquired sufficient knowledge and skills in various trainings will be able to fully apply this knowledge while participating in rescue operations in real conditions. Because each person has different physical capabilities and character aspects according to their natural state. It is the spiritual preparation of the rescuer that takes center stage in this real situation. Mental endurance, stability ensures that the rescuer

can fully apply the acquired knowledge and skills in any situation. That is why it is necessary to pay special attention to the spiritual training, which is one of the important stages of preparation. It is of particular importance to conduct the theoretical training of this training with the involvement of psychologists from medical institutions, and to ensure the participation of rescuers with many years of experience in the practical training.

It is practically impossible to fully implement the set of measures to ensure the safety of rescuers that we have discussed above in a day or two. For this, of course, certain factors such as time, attention and continuity are required. The next two factors - attention and continuity - are extremely important in places. It is necessary for local leaders to allocate time to relevant specialists for the implementation of these activities, to ensure the full participation of rescuers in the conducted trainings, and in general to pay special attention to this direction. Also, it is necessary to finish all the work started in this direction on time, and to continue the activities carried out throughout the year. Because it is negative to hold events in this regard during a certain time of the year and not during a certain time consequences take will come

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